

Graphical Abstract

Towards real-time, in-line characterization of unidirectional fiber composites

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Highlights

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- A plenoptic acquisition geometry and reconstruction pipeline is described, which faithfully reconstructs 3D volumes of unidirectional fiber composites. Using simulated and experimental data, the technique is verified and compared with conventional CT. The framework has potential for being implemented in an in-line manufacturing setting.

Towards real-time, in-line characterization of unidirectional fiber composites

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Abstract

Local fiber alignment and microstructure greatly influence the overall performance of components in unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites. Characterization of local microstructure and fiber alignment are critical in determining the performance of CFRP parts. However, detecting and accurately quantifying microstructural properties remains a challenge. Traditional X-ray computed tomography (CT) provides high-resolution three-dimensional imaging, but is often limited to *ex-situ* or post-mortem sample characterization due to acquisition time and setup complexity. We propose a prototype imaging and reconstruction framework for plenoptic X-ray data acquisition, demonstrating feasibility as a real-time in-line characterization technique for CFRP materials. We discuss the geometry, implementation and limitations of plenoptic acquisition schemes in contrast to conventional CT. The technique is applied to simulated and experimental data, and various material properties of interest are extracted from both CT and plenoptic reconstructions.

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Composite materials such as carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) and glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) composites play an important role in

a variety of industries, such as air, land, and sea vehicles, and wind turbines, due to their high stiffness, strength, and low density [1, 2].

The microstructure and fiber orientation is a crucial property to consider in the design of CFRP components and depends on the application. In the case of wind turbine blades, unidirectional composites are often favored to maximize the fatigue lifetime given the encountered stress environment during usage [3]. Such unidirectional composites are designed to have a high degree of alignment between carbon fibers along a single axis [4]. This type of CFRP configuration is typically achieved by a manufacturing process such as pultrusion, whereby fibers are pulled in tension along a single axis from a series of spindles through a resin bath and cured along a single production line.

The performance of unidirectional composites is heavily affected by microstructural defects such as voids, cracks, splicing defects, and microstructural parameters such as fiber alignment and volume fraction of fibers [5, 6, 7]. A detailed analysis of local microstructure is therefore important in identifying and rectifying these defects, preferably by in-line optimization during manufacturing.

X-ray based methods, such as computational tomography (CT), allow for a full 3D reconstruction of the cross-section, but typically the time resolution and setup complexity cause significant challenges for being deployed in real time in an in-line environment.

Typically, CT requires a minimum number of projections (n_{proj}) dictated by the Nyquist criterion in order for a reconstruction to be sufficiently sampled. However, many iterative methods exist that can produce satisfactory results from a much smaller n_{proj} . By reducing the number and range of projections, the time-cost and setup requirements can be reduced and present a step towards developing an in-line real-time characterization pipeline setting on a competitive time scale.

Plenoptic imaging is a technique that allows computational refocusing after acquisition in the visible light regime from a single-shot photograph from an array of micro-lenses. It has been shown that the plenoptic geometry can be emulated in the X-ray regime through a series of source and detector translations, demonstrating the feasibility of limited-angle X-ray 3D reconstruction from a single shot acquisition (i.e., a series of projections acquired at a single moment in time) [8, 9]. Given the reduced sampling domain requirements of a unidirectional composite, the sampling achieved via a plenoptic acquisition geometry in the X-ray regime is well-suited towards

accurately characterizing these types of samples. Alternative methods to CT have been investigated as candidates to address the time-scale problem for in-line characterization, such as X-ray tomosynthesis for the characterization of larger-scale defects[10]. In contrast, the aim of a plenoptic imaging acquisition geometry is to be able to characterize the microstructure on the scale of individual fibers, such that fiber alignment and fiber volume fraction can be monitored under real-time manufacturing conditions.

We present a reconstruction framework based on an experimental configuration similar to the demonstration by Vigano et al. [8] for plenoptic imaging with X-rays. We demonstrate its use with both simulated and experimental data, and show its feasibility as a real-time acquisition scheme capable of producing a 3D reconstruction of a carbon-fiber composite. Taking advantage of the in-line geometry of the prototype, we combine datasets from several different sample translations along a single axis, which represent the equivalent of a time-step in a production environment. Several time-steps can be incorporated into a single reconstruction in order to improve the overall fidelity.

Figure 1: The proposed setup of a plenoptic acquisition geometry for in-line imaging. The workpiece, after shaping, passes through the center of an array of sources and detectors, imaging a small cross-section of the workpiece and creating a 3D reconstruction of the region of interest (ROI). a. Carbon fiber spools are pulled forward in the pultrusion direction. b. Resin bath through which the fibers are pulled and cured. c. Heated die that shapes the workpiece into the desired cross-section. d. The formed workpiece. e. the set of source arrays f. their corresponding detector array positions. g. the ROI of the cross-section that is imaged. h. the direction of pultrusion i. the reconstructed volume of the ROI

Fig. 1 is a schematic of the proposed in-line implementation of a single-shot plenoptic imaging rig. The top image shows the key components of a pultrusion rig. We introduce the coordinate system as shown in the upper right-hand corner, with z being the pultrusion direction along which the fibers are aligned, with x and y being orthogonal to this direction. Rolls or spools of carbon fiber (Fig. 1a.) are threaded into a tension roller and drawn into a resin bath (Fig. 1b.). The resin permeates the fibers in the bath, which are then drawn into a heated die (Fig. 1c.), which defines the cross-section of the workpiece and creates the densely packed shape of the final product. Following the heated die, the workpiece is gradually pulled along (Fig. 1 h.) by further downstream pulling mechanisms and cut into

appropriate lengths or rolled up for storage.

The proposed implementation of a plenoptic imaging setup (Fig. 1e. to 1g.) is placed in the production line after the material exits the heated die. The plenoptic setup has two arrays, an array of sources (Fig. 1e.) and a corresponding detector array (Fig. 1f.). Each source-detector pair is geometrically opposed (indicated by red lines between panels), where, assuming the origin of the entire array lies at (x, y, z) , detector at position $(x + dx, y + dy, z_{det})$ acquires a projection illuminated from source at position $(x - dx, y - dy, z_{source})$. The workpiece passes through the middle of the source and detector arrays, and the acquisition geometry closely mimics that of limited-angle CT. The region of interest (ROI) (1g.) that is illuminated by the array is reconstructed into a 3D volume (1i.). The setup is designed to work in near real-time, with the extent of the workpiece cross-section in x, y assumed to be within the entire field of view (FOV). The setup collects a single-shot at a particular moment in time t_0 , which, given the workpiece in pultrusion is continually moving along z , corresponds to position z_0 . Subsequent acquisitions in time (t_1, t_2, \dots) each have corresponding z positions (z_1, z_2, \dots) and can be used to characterize larger ROIs of the workpiece.

2. Methods

For experimentally acquired data, the plenoptic array is emulated by a laboratory CT setup with a single source and a movable detector. Source positions are emulated by equivalent translations of the sample. The detector used is an Advacam advapix TPX3, with a detector pixel size of $55 \mu\text{m}$. The source-sample distance is 13 mm, with a sample to detector distance of 113 mm, giving an optical magnification factor of about 10. The effective pixel size is therefore approximately $5 \mu\text{m}$.

The sample piece used is a glass-fiber reinforced composite (GFRP) produced via pultrusion, that is cut down to a cube with sides of 1 mm, with an average fiber diameter of 10-15 μm , giving an average resolution of 2-3 pixels per fiber. The acquisition time was 60 seconds per projection.

For experimentally acquired data, the sample is imaged both with the plenoptic geometry as described in Fig. 1, and in standard CT geometry where the sample is rotated about a single axis with projections acquired over a range of angles from 0 to 180 degrees. Henceforth, we refer to this standard CT as "rotational geometry", in contrast to plenoptic geometry.

Reconstructions are performed using the ASTRA toolbox with Pytorch as a wrapper, using the ADAM optimizer, effectively performing an iterative reconstruction using automatic differentiation. Non-negativity constraints are applied, and total variation regularization along the fiber direction is also applied.

For simulated data, phantoms are generated using the fiber-pack package available on GitHub[11]. A sample case plenoptic reconstruction notebook for simulated data is also available on GitHub under the package PlenoXFiber[12].

3. Results

3.1. Simulated data

First, the effect of n_{proj} on reconstruction quality was investigated and compared with reconstructions produced from rotational geometry. Fig. 2 shows a single slice in the xy plane of a reconstructed volume from a series of projections acquired in plenoptic geometry (second column). n_{proj} increases in each row from top to bottom (starting with a minimum of a 4×4 square array of source-detector pair positions, going up to a maximum of 21×21). The outer columns of Fig. 2 correspond to the error of the slice, calculated as the square of the absolute difference between the reconstruction and the volume for each pixel, while the bottom scatter plot shows the behavior of mean error as a function of n_{proj} . It can be seen that even at $n_{\text{proj}} = 121$, individual fibers can be resolved quite well from a relatively small n_{proj} . For comparison, the same slice for reconstructions produced from rotational geometry is shown (third column). Especially for lower n_{proj} , the plenoptic reconstruction performs significantly better, and the difference in error between the two geometries vanishes as n_{proj} is increased.

Figure 2: Plenoptic reconstructions of a cross-section of carbon fibers from a simulated volume. Each image represents an increasing n_{proj} . Inner columns: Reconstructions of a single xy slice for plenoptic (inner left) and rotational geometry (inner right) geometries. Outer two columns: square error between the reconstruction and the ground truth slice for plenoptic (outer left) and rotational geometry (outer right). Bottom: the mean error of a slice as a function of n_{proj} .

In conventional CT, the relationship between the size of an imaged object, the achievable resolution, and the number of required projections is given by the Crowther criterion[13]:

$$n_{\text{proj}} = \pi D/d \quad (1)$$

where D is the size of the object and d is the desired spatial resolution. Given the size of the detector is a square array of 256^2 pixels, and a fiber covers approximately 4-6 pixels, a target resolution of half the fiber diameter (i.e., approximately 2 pixels) requires a minimum $n_{\text{proj}} \approx 402$. With added information and constraints, iterative reconstruction techniques are capable of producing sufficient resolution with fewer projections than what is strictly estimated by the Crowther Criterion. It can be seen in Fig. 2 that the mean error of the slice tends to plateau around $n_{\text{proj}} = 225$ for rotational geometry. In all cases, the mean error is lower for plenoptic reconstructions of the same volume with the same n_{proj} , but the difference between the two vanishes as n_{proj} is increased.

Figure 3: The average error of plenoptic reconstructions as a function of n_{proj} . The blue inset shows the typical distribution of source-detector pair positions, except for the red data point, where the positions are shifted to the edges of the same area, resulting in a reduced error for a fixed n_{proj} .

Fig. 3 shows the change in error as a function of n_{proj} . Typically, all plenoptic geometries follow a raster array with evenly spaced positions within

a fixed square of 0.4 m in x and y , as can be seen in the blue inset. Such a distribution of source-detector positions is chosen for simplicity and as a starting point for experimental investigation of plenoptic geometry, but the effect of varying the distribution of these positions while keeping n_{proj} fixed was also investigated. This can be seen in the red inset, which corresponds to the red data point. In this case, all positions are placed at the edges of the square array, resulting in a reduced error for equivalent n_{proj} . This suggests that n_{proj} can be further reduced by optimization of the geometry of source-detector pair positions.

3.1.1. Sampling considerations (Fourier space)

The basis for sampling considerations in 3D reconstruction is given by the Crowther criterion[13], which states that the number of angles N_θ required to fully sample the Fourier domain of an object of size D at spatial resolution d is given by $N_\theta \simeq \pi D/d$. In a 2D sample case, each projection corresponds to a single line of the Fourier domain of the sample, and angles θ are distributed evenly from 0 to 180, with a sufficiently large N_θ to fully sample the image in Fourier space, whereas in plenoptic imaging, the sampled area of Fourier space is much more limited, covering a small range of U_z [14].

In an idealized 3D fiber sample with all fibers perfectly aligned to a given axis, e.g., the z axis, the variation along this direction should be effectively zero, meaning that the amount of sample information in the Fourier domain along the corresponding axis U_z should be centered around $U_z = 0$, with little to no high frequency information in U_z . The majority of the sample information in the Fourier domain, therefore, lies along the axes normal to U_z , i.e., along U_x and U_y . For such an anisotropic sample and for a fixed n_{proj} , a series of projections evenly spaced across θ is not the most optimal sampling. We believe this to be the basis for why plenoptic reconstructions perform better for equivalent n_{proj} compared to rotational geometry.

Figure 4: Sampling of different geometries in Fourier space. a) The real volume. b) the 3D Fourier Transform of the structure, with zero-frequency components shifted to the center. c) The planes of the Fourier domain sampled in a typical plenoptic geometry (only x-axis positions shown). d) The planes of the Fourier domain sampled in rotational geometry. In such an anisotropic sample, most of the information lies around $U_z = 0$, and for a fixed n_{proj} , many of the angles in rotational geometry do not sample much information.

To illustrate this schematically, Fig. 4 shows where the volume is sampled in 3-dimensional Fourier space, with planes sampled by the chosen angular range in both plenoptic and CT geometries. It can be seen that for a fixed n_{proj} , the angles imaged in a plenoptic geometry better correlate with the frequency distribution in Fourier space for an anisotropic CFRP phantom, compared to rotational geometry, where many angles are used to sample regions of Fourier space where there is little sample information.

It should be noted that the visualizations for Fourier space sampling in Fig. 4 are based on the approximation of treating the geometry as a limited-angle CT where the detector plane is normal to each X-ray source vector. In reality, all detectors lie in a single plane that is normal to z . For a more thorough discussion of the differences that this causes in Fourier space sampling, we refer to Section 2.6 of Vigano et al.[14].

3.2. Experimental data

Figure 5: plenoptic and rotational geometry reconstructions from experimental data. Left: plenoptic, $n_t = 1$. Middle: plenoptic, $n_t = 2$. Right: Conventional rotational geometry. Top row: slices along xy plane (normal to fibers) Bottom row: slices along xz plane (parallel to fibers)

Fig. 5 shows plenoptic reconstructions from experimental data on the 1 mm cube glass fiber sample. For each row, there are three images, corresponding to a different number of time-steps (n_t) multiple plenoptic arrays with different z -positions) $n_t = 1$, $n_t = 2$, and rotational geometry. The top row shows a slice of the volume in the xy plane (normal to the direction of fiber orientation), whereas the bottom row shows a slice of the volume in the xz plane, parallel to fiber orientations. The distance in z between each time step is 0.5 mm. With the addition of extra time steps, the contrast between fiber cross-sections in the xy plane is greatly enhanced. The plenoptic reconstruction tends to best resolve contrast in the xy plane, or in the plane of the reconstructed volume parallel to the detector plane, as shown in Fig. 1. Sample features far away from this plane tend to be undersampled in plenoptic geometry, which is why the fidelity of the plenoptic reconstruction in the

xz plane tends to show a much poorer correlation with the reconstructed rotational geometry.

In principle, fully sampled rotational geometry should always provide the highest quality reconstruction, but due to the fact that multiple time steps allow for a larger n_{proj} , this explains why the $n_t = 2$ reconstruction appears better than the rotational geometry. It should be noted that some zero-values appear within the volume in Fig. 5 in the xz slice for $n_t = 2$, which implies these regions are voids as they have the same value as the background. It can be seen in the corresponding areas in the CT that this is not the case. We attribute this to the flux of all projections changing when the source-sample distance is varied and not adequately captured by a single flat field, resulting in an inaccurate normalization during treatment of projection data. This is discussed further in section 4.1.

The contrast between fibers in Fig. 5 for $n_t = 2$ also appears to be exaggerated in contrast to the CT reconstruction. We again attribute this to incorrect normalization of the set of plenoptic projections.

Figure 6: An example of the 'cross talk' between slices that occur in plenoptic reconstructions as exact cross-sections are not cleanly resolved

Fig. 6 shows an xy slice from another location in the volume. It can be seen that fiber cross-sections are not resolved as cleanly into circular cross-sections as in Fig. 5. What can be observed is a 'cross-talk' as parts of the fiber in neighboring slices located at $\pm\Delta z$ tend to bleed into any given xy slice, making individual fiber cross-section identification more difficult. This is in contrast to the rotational geometry reconstruction, which has a uniform

level of fiber separation throughout the volume and all slices having relatively "circular" cross-sections of fibers.

3.3. Material Properties

Table 1 shows calculated material properties of interest for GFRPs from the reconstructions. The first 3 columns indicate calculations from simulated data, whereas the last two are for reconstructions from experimental data. In the case of experimental data, there is no ground truth to compare to, as the true value of V_f is not verified independently. For simulated data, comparisons with the ground truth object can be made. It appears the plenoptic reconstruction underestimates V_f , whereas the rotational geometry reconstruction overestimates the result. Both are within $\pm 5\%$ of the true value. In the case of mean fiber diameter, the plenoptic reconstruction achieves a result closer to the true value than rotational geometry, with an error of 3% and 8%, respectively.

Fiber orientations computed from volume reconstructions can be estimated using structure tensor analysis [15, 16, 17]. Using the *structure-tensor* package by Jeppesen et al. [16], the structure tensor was calculated for both the rotational geometry and plenoptic reconstruction of the same sample. Fig. 7 shows the distribution of orientations centered around the z axis in the yz plane, whereas Table 2 shows the calculated properties of the distributions. For structure tensor calculations, the plenoptic reconstruction with $n_t = 1$ is used, due to the enhanced contrast visible in $n_t = 2$, causing an exaggerated effect of orientation parallel to z . The values in Fig. 7 are a fractional distribution of the eigenvector of the z direction, normalized by the number of elements in the volume. The values in Table 2 are computed from a Gaussian fit of each distribution in Fig. 7.

Parameter	GT (S)	Plenoptic (S)	CT (S)	Plenoptic (E)	CT (E)
Volume Fraction (V_f)	0.41	0.37	0.45	0.39	0.45
Mean Fiber Diameter (μm)	6.2(0.7)	6.4(1.1)	6.7(1.1)	11.6(3.6)	11.3(3.3)

Table 1: Comparison of calculated material properties of interest for CFRP composites from plenoptic and CT (rotational geometry) reconstructions of the same sample. Numbers in parenthesis indicate standard deviation of mean fiber diameter. **S** = simulated data. **E** = experimental data.

Figure 7: The distribution of the structure tensor computed around the z axis, i.e., an angle of 0 corresponds to parallel with the z axis in the yz plane.

	μ (degrees)	σ (degrees)
CT	1.41	2.7
Plenoptic	1.04	2.3

Table 2: Structure tensor parameters, the mean angle (μ) and standard deviation (σ) for each reconstruction method

It can be seen that the standard deviation (μ) is larger for the rotational geometry reconstruction. This is due to the fact that the plenoptic reconstruction has difficulty reconstructing higher-angle features (i.e., fibers that have higher degrees of misalignment with respect to the z axis as shown in Fig. 1. Only reconstructing fibers accurately that have a lower degree of misorientation will tend to bias the structure tensor distribution to only capture lower-angle features (fibers with low misorientation), resulting in a narrower distribution.

4. Discussion

4.1. Projection Normalization

The reconstructions in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 show some zero-values of absorption in the reconstructed volumes. This is incorrect, as it implies the presence of voids in these regions, whereas it can be seen in the corresponding areas of the sample in CT that these values are non-zero. We attribute this discrepancy due to the method of normalization. In rotational CT, flat field correction is normally performed by acquiring a flat field image immediately before and/or after a scan has been acquired, which is then used to

normalize projections [18]. A single flat field image is typically sufficient for an entire CT scan, where the detector and source are typically fixed in space. In plenoptic geometry, the distance between source and detector is different for each source-detector position, and so normalization by a single flat field for the entire set of plenoptic projections may not be sufficient. Instead, we propose that in the future, a full set of flat field images for each source-array pair position is acquired to ensure correct normalizations of projections prior to reconstruction. In the reconstructions shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, only a single flat field image was used for projection normalization.

4.2. Structure Tensor

It can be seen that in Fig. 7 and Table. 2 that the predicted distribution of fibers is wider in the case of rotational geometry and narrower in the case of plenoptic. This may be an effect of fibers with larger degrees of misorientation not being reconstructed as well in plenoptic geometry, which is approximately limited to fibers with a degree of orientation smaller than the largest sampled angles in a given plenoptic geometry. Thus, the distribution of orientations will be biased towards the center as highly misoriented fibers (fibers with large angles away from z) are effectively excluded in structure tensor calculations by not being reconstructed as effectively as in a fully-sampled rotational geometry. This can be mitigated by increasing the maximum angle captured in a plenoptic array, by widening the distribution of the source-detector pair array for a given sample to detector distance.

5. Conclusion

We have demonstrated a plenoptic acquisition geometry and reconstruction pipeline that faithfully reconstructs 3D volumes of unidirectional fiber composites, using simulated and experimental data, with potential for being implemented in an in-line manufacturing setting.

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